

CERTAIN ASPECTS OF VIEWS IN MODERN INTERPRETATION OF THE CONTENT OF CATEGORIES “MEDIA”, “POLITICAL CONSCIOUSNESS” AND “YOUTH POLITICAL CONSCIOUSNESS”

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ANNOTATION

This article examines aspects related to the life of the state and society, as well as the media, political consciousness and political awareness of youth, which are important in the education of youth. In particular, the analysis of the media, definitions of the concept of political consciousness and related views are presented as a reflection of the realities that take place in the life of society. Naturally, the author focused on this topic from the strategy of actions in the life of today's country to the evolutionism of reforms carried out within the framework of the development strategy, and drew conclusions in connection with these processes.

Basic concepts: Media, political consciousness, youth political consciousness, youth, sustainable development, public life, civil society.

INTRODUCTION

The democratic processes taking place in the life of the country are directly and indirectly linked to the political consciousness of the media and youth. Naturally, the sustainable development of society's life is primarily measured by youth policy and the maturity of the youth worldview, political and legal consciousness that formed its basis. At the new stage of Uzbekistan's national development, the issue of the political identity of our people, nation, and youth will be relevant in the implementation of priority tasks determined by the principle of "from national recovery to national recovery" and the concept of the development strategy from the very beginning. the strategy of action. We can observe this not only in the following processes, but also in the pragmatic aspects of the theory. The media, as a symbolic fourth power, is associated with the control of the activities of all three authorities (legislative, judicial and executive), as well as such processes as ensuring the evolutionarily of reforms in society, informing the population about the news of socio-political processes, reforms, its role in solving problems in socio-political, spiritual- economic spheres, together with modern society, can rightfully be called

information time. First of all, this refers to the global nature of the press, which has a profound impact on the mass consciousness. Today, it is safe to say that the information society is a separate world, a separate world that controls our thoughts, tries to adjust our consciousness to itself and serves to provide an additional material base in the form of a current audience. Currently, it is difficult to imagine the stability of society without the media. Of course, the media is an integral part of political life, and the development strategy that determines the fate of our people, our country, and the path of development is a guarantee of great development that embodies the interests and aspirations of our people, so to speak, will not be mistaken.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND METHODS

As part of the scientific research on the topic "the content of the categories "media", "political consciousness" and "youth political consciousness", some aspects of views on modern interpretation", the following scientific literature was studied in detail. Political consciousness of student youth of small and medium-sized businesses. -large cities according to M. A. Kalugina: problems and ways of formation: RUSSIA on the example of the Far East: dis.... candidate of Pedagogical Sciences. Candidate of Political Sciences: 23.00.02, Vladivostok, 2007; Prepared by I. P. Yakusheva. "The modern youth movement as a factor of activation of political consciousness in Russian society: abstract. Candidate of Political Sciences: 23.00.02. - M., 2007; Social integration of youth in an unstable society / Yu.A.Zubok. - M.: Sosium, 1998; Danilin P. New youth policy. - M.: Europe, 2006; Kalinicheva S. A. The system of higher professional education of the Russian Federation as an institute for the formation of political consciousness of youth: dis....candidate of Pedagogical Sciences. Candidate of Political Sciences: 23.00.02; H.M. Formation of political consciousness of youth in the context of perestroika according to Khalidov: dis. Candidate of Political Sciences: Philos. the candidate. Sciences: 09.00.02. - M., 1990; M. M. Bugakov, on the other hand, we are talking about the peculiarities of the formation of political consciousness of youth in the conditions of developed socialism: Dis. Candidate philos. Sciences: 09.00.01. - M., 1984; Formation of political consciousness of students of economic universities in the conditions of socialism, developed in scientific research V. A. Kondakov-x: Dis. Candidate philos. Sciences: 09.00.02. - M., 1984. The topic of social reproduction, developed under the guidance of V.I. Chuprov, makes it possible to reveal the role of youth in the process of restoring socio-political relations, to identify the mechanisms of development of the younger generation in this area. Another area developed by the Department of Youth Sociology to study changes in important characteristics of the political consciousness of youth in the context of transformation and its inherent uncertainty

and danger is risk (Yu.A.ZUBOK, Considering that in the context of transformation, the team of authors studies various aspects of the formation of political consciousness. It should be noted that the works of domestic scientists, Professors I.Siafnazarov, S.Otamuratov, V. Kuchkarov, were carried out in harmony with the problems of political consciousness, political identity and political culture in general, issues of globalization and national identity, and are also awaiting their research in today's renewing Uzbekistan. When covering the topic, methods such as analysis, synthesis, system analysis, historicism, content analysis and the like were used.

RESULTS

For the life of society and its sustainable development, as well as the foundations of national statehood, the formation of ideas about information and events has been important since time immemorial. Many tasks related to those who come and go from the state, events and events, the transmission of messages such as the welfare of the people, the reforms carried out in the life of the country have been implemented. When classifying theoretical approaches to the media, researchers turn to a number of sociological theories, in particular to institutional theory, theory of social systems, theory of social spheres.

Media research in Western countries proves that the impact of this phenomenon on consumers of information is great. For most researchers, according to the general understanding of the media, it is a social institution that interacts with various spheres of public life (social sphere, Politics, Economics, Culture, personal life, etc.), while another theoretical approach, widely accepted, recognizes the media as a separate industry.

To determine the dictionary meaning of the word "information", it is necessary to compare the word "message" and the word "information". Both of these words are Arabic, message - "to transmit information", "to give information"; report – the plural of the word message; - noun-a suffix forming the plural, joining the noun in Arabic. In the Uzbek language, both the message and the information are used in the singular to mean “message” [1].

A group of Uzbek philosophers and historians interprets the word “information” as follows: “information is information that uses prepared information in order to increase accuracy about something (process, phenomenon). Information-information obtained from the environment (sources), prepared for consumption. Information provides information about events and events in consumption. Reveals the essence of phenomena and events [2].”

The Russian scientist-philosopher V.D. Popov interprets information from a socio-philosophical point of view - synthesized: “information in a broad sense is the

result of the existence of society and the reflection of existing facts in its consciousness in various manifestations. On the other hand, in a narrow (functional, social) sense, information is circulation, transmission in the form of a message, which reflects the versatility of the life of society [3].”

The transformation of mass media into a subject of scientific research can also be explained by the fact that the study of the patterns of development of the media industry as a developed and profitable branch of the economy is important.

It should be noted that media studies clarify the complexity of the nature of modern mass media*. This, in turn, causes the growth of theoretical approaches.

In generalizing theoretical approaches to mass media, the researcher of information theory, turn to Let's turn to the Dutch sociologist D McQuil. The scientist suggests studying the mass media for two reasons. The first is related to their role in society, understanding the ways of interaction and influence between them [4]. In the same aspect, D.McQuail divides concepts based on media-oriented and socially oriented approaches into two large groups. Media-oriented theories presuppose a huge autonomy of the media within the framework of socio-political and economic systems. At the same time, the media act as a single source of changes taking place both in the media system and in society. On the other hand, with a socially oriented approach, the priority will be processes that go beyond the media system. These processes, causing changes in society, act as a factor in the reformulation of the media.

In the process of studying the mass media, it becomes necessary to identify the relationship between spiritual and material factors in order to highlight existing approaches. The cultural approach involves the perception of the media, concepts such as “idea”, “value”, which they promote. On the other hand, media studies based on a materialistic approach explore the structure and relationships of personal property, paying special attention to the functioning and development of the media in a market economy.

The economic and political approach to studying the activities of the media today is one of the progressive, primary approaches. This approach includes a number of works aimed at studying the imbalances of the global information flow. Back in the 1960s, these studies expressed the need to develop the political economy of the media.

The discussions on information imperialism in the 80s and the proposals put forward by the Sean McBride Committee for the Study of UNESCO Communication Problems on the development of a new information order focused primarily on the uneven and unfair distribution of information and communications between countries, regions and continents [5].

The point of view of the Italian scientist Antonio Gramsci [6] on this matter is also interesting. He notes that the main function of the mass media is connected with the process of incorporation, that is, with the formation of the main links of the worldview, which give all structures of society the opportunity to promote themselves, first of all, the economic interests of the dominant groups as the interests of the whole society.

DISCUSSION

According to the typology of the media, which are mentioned in the scientific literature, there are 5 main types. These are: the press (newspapers, magazines, newsletters, etc.), radio, television, news agencies, as well as Internet sites. Internet sites, which today attract the attention of many, or rather are positioned as a kind of mass media, are characterized by greater speed and breadth of coverage than other types.

As the Ukrainian publicist G.Pochepsov notes: “People can watch much more on television than in newspapers. According to him, 69% of the information transmitted on television is not described in words. At the same time, it is observed that half of the audience remembers what they saw. When news is described by voice, 16% of people remember it, and 34% remember News described only by an image. 32% of people made a mistake when they were asked to retell the news described aloud, and only 15% made the mistake of retelling the news described only with images [7].”

Analysis is the main advantage of the press. If television works for “everyone”, the radio is intended for the “lazy and hasty”, and the newspaper is intended for the “smartest” or those who want to see themselves that way, and the newspaper is constantly read mainly by people with higher education. Nevertheless, the newspaper's capabilities are not without some drawbacks, not every newspaper surpasses radio and television in the field of emotional impact. Thus, although the press lags behind other industries in terms of efficiency and emotionality, it has an advantage over the rest in terms of analysis. This allows you to confidently and deeply influence the minds of the audience. Television and radio information quickly attracts attention, but is quickly forgotten. And the article covered by the newspaper will remain in the memory for a long time.

Online media. The name of the Internet, which is widespread in the world today, is the “web” (English - Word Wide Web, i.e. “world Wide Web”, abbreviated WWW), the name of which can give an accurate idea of it. Imagine a spider that surrounds the entire globe, its web is a communication network, and the connections of the web are computers. One computer is linked to another by a web of several

thousand, the system is designed in such a way that even if any of them is damaged, it will not greatly affect the communication between the two computers. Every computer connected to the network cannot get the necessary information from an address in the outside world until it gets access to a specific ip address. Therefore, the network address (for example, www.yahoo.com, www.mail.ru and other similar addresses). If someone had said, "the Internet has everything," they would have been a little right about the Internet. Because in the imagination of many, the Internet appears as a kind of "virtual reality" space. Experts say that today more than 200 million computers around the world are connected to the Internet.

World experience shows that on the path of development of any democratic society, information finds its expression only when its functional function acquires the primary goal of serving national interests. In the process of transition from a strong state to a strong civil society, the formation and development of public opinion, the interaction of state and civil institutions, it also occupies a leading place as an important tool. The state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of informatization is aimed at creating a national information system taking into account modern world principles of development and improvement of information resources, information technologies and information systems [8]. The main directions of the state policy in the field of informatization are:

- * the realization of the constitutional rights of everyone to free access and dissemination of information, ensuring access to information resources;

- * creation of a unified information space of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on information systems of state bodies, network and territorial information systems, as well as information systems of legal entities and individuals;

- * creation of conditions for the use of international information networks and the worldwide Internet information network;

- * formation of state information resources, creation and development of information systems, ensuring their compatibility and interaction;

- * organization of production of modern information technology tools;

- assistance in the formation of the market of information resources, services and information technologies;

- * development and promotion of software production;

- * support and stimulation of entrepreneurship, creation of favorable conditions for attracting investments;

- * training and advanced training of personnel, stimulation of scientific research.

An important place in the formation of the national informatization system, accelerating the introduction of modern information technologies in all spheres and

regulating its legal foundations is occupied by current laws, presidential decrees, Cabinet resolutions and other normative acts.

Over the past years of our independence, the mass media in our country have passed a peculiar path of political progress and today have become an integral part of a right-wing democratic state and a free civil society, an impartial voice-the word of our people.

President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev sent congratulations on June 27 - the Day of Press and Media Workers. The head of state stressed that “Our country is well aware that in the current period, when our country is entering a new and important stage of its development, representatives of the media sphere — journalists and editors, directors and cameramen, bloggers, employees of television and radio channels, newspapers and magazines, publishing houses and printing houses make an invaluable contribution to the formation of a democratic image of our Homeland glorification of her to the whole world, and highly appreciates them”. Indeed, the President noted that the number of mass media in the country had increased by almost 30 percent compared to 2016 before 1962, and, in particular, recognized that private media play an important role in ensuring the diversity of opinions in society, carrying out fundamental reforms, and boldly solving problems and shortcomings allowed in the places. It was also emphasized that the number of online publications in the national information space has almost doubled over the past 6 years to 677[9].

Naturally, the media plays an important role in educating young people and shaping their worldview. At the same time, a detailed study of the concepts of political consciousness and political identity serves to highlight the problem more widely. Political consciousness is one of the main forms of social consciousness that arises together with the emergence of political power and statehood. In the most general sense, political consciousness is the totality of all theoretical and spontaneous political ideas and attitudes that exist in a given period of time. It is correct to say that political consciousness is the perception of political actors about the use of society's resources for its safe development. Political consciousness is divided into several types: individual (includes a system of information, motivational and value components that ensure an individual's knowledge of politics and participation in it);

group (summarizes the attitudes and motives of political behavior of certain classes, strata, elites);

mass (express public opinion, moods and mass actions).

Personal political consciousness is formed in the process of political socialization and expresses a person's ability to evaluate politics and the nature of their attitude to activity in it. There are different views on the “political consciousness”, which each researcher treated from the point of view of his research.

Research in this area was mainly conducted by political scientists and lawyers. Political consciousness was first defined in the textbook for higher educational institutions of the republic on the discipline "political science" as follows: "political consciousness is a system of perception, perception, cognition, evaluation of the political sphere by a specific individual, group, layers. Political consciousness is a set of people's knowledge about the political system and life, political relations, ideas, advice, beliefs, assessments of the political system in which they live [10]." In another textbook, "political consciousness is associated with the processes of political socialization of the individual. The political socialization of an individual is a connection between the formation of political ideas about political life, the formation of skills of political activity and their transformation into a certain level of culture [11].

As is known, the process of political socialization in the process of an individual's life activity does not remain without a direct impact on the political system, development, behavior, status of society, as well as on the political consciousness and culture of the individual. Political independence and national identity strongly influence people's political views. From the above, we can say that political consciousness is a set of political ideas, views, skills and knowledge about political processes. When we talk about political processes, we mean, first of all, the state power, its activities in political management and the political relations that take place in it. They are diverse and can develop evenly or reach a high level. How they proceed will depend on the level at which the State government organizes political governance.

Political consciousness begins to form among the people living in it with the advent of the state. At the heart of this is the problem of whether the State can pursue policies that represent its interests. In both these cases, a person forms his attitude to the activities of state power in its political management. More specifically, political consciousness arises as the perception of a person's political interests. Consequently, when we talk about political interests, a person realizes his economic, social, spiritual and educational needs "through" the participation of state power. But the state, for objective and subjective reasons, can never fully satisfy the needs of the individual, and it does not have the capabilities. Because the more comfortable a person lives, the higher his needs are. This is an objective process, the increase of the same needs is a factor leading the country and the person to progress. If the process of increasing needs stops, it also leads to a halt in progress. The development of political consciousness in this process, the inability of the state power to function in accordance with the increasing political needs in political management creates a situation where the citizens express their attitude towards it. It is in this state that a

person begins to form views, ideas and skills on the political activities of state power. They will continue to develop in accordance with the progress of the State authorities. With political consciousness, the political socialization of the individual becomes mutually exclusive. This is synchronized with the “political consciousness of the youth”. When we talk about the political socialization of an individual, we mean strengthening his understanding of political processes and participation in them. The concept of socialization, used in a broad sense along with political socialization, is also used in science. It implies the participation of an individual in all spheres of society, in this aspect it is broader than the concept of “political socialization”, and, in turn, covers it. It is supposed to show the place of socialization of youth in the movement. In fact, the political socialization of an individual simultaneously with the development of his political consciousness leads to the development of his participation in society not only in political processes, but also in economic, social, spiritual and educational processes. Thus, political consciousness acts as an indicator that ensures the functioning of the individual in all spheres of activity.

CONCLUSION

In general, the study of the media and the political consciousness of youth is a criterion that is not only considered as a simple perception of socio-political processes, but also represents it in a broader sense, that is, as a mature person with his life goals in government and society and sustainable development. After all, another important indicator of political culture in the activities of state power is that it manifests itself in reliance not on power in political management, but on the principles of justice, trust and political restraint. The state as a political institution has a very complex socio-political structure. It has a person, a personality, a citizen, a nation, a people, public organizations, political forces, and the interests of each of them are also applicable. The diversity of interests in itself always remains a source of conflict between them. In the event of such a conflict, an important reason for their resolution is that the State has reached a level of respect for the principles of justice, trust and political restraint.

A certain position in the life of society is occupied by that part of the youth who is interested in politics and is inclined to participate in political processes. Because they are associated with: 1) to occupy a certain position in power; 2) to satisfy their political interests, economic, social and spiritual and educational needs by their participation in the life of power; 3) in order for everyone to achieve their political "I"; 4) in order to achieve political stability in state power and society. 5) achieving a full guarantee of their rights to remuneration; 6) participation in the adoption of laws that serve the development of the country and the welfare of the people, their application

in real practice; 7) achieving the expression of the interests of all youth in domestic and foreign policy pursued in the country; 8) strengthening the interaction of youth with other social classes in society, a single force on the path of development of the country and the welfare of the people. the idea is to act like.

Thus, the functioning of the mass media in democratic processes is determined by:

- in attracting intellectuals and people with an emerging social consciousness to cooperation;
- in the formation of public opinion; to promote the expansion of opportunities for the real participation of the broad masses in political processes;
 - carries out political integration work taking into account the assimilation of the prevailing political values, ideas, attitudes, and their imaginary perception by people;
- in establishing a dialogue, a dialogue between citizens and society, the state;
- in the promotion and promotion of cutting-edge ideas, works or group activities;
- in the promotion and evaluation of historical and cultural values, humanistic heritage;
- in awakening a positive attitude towards ethno social processes;
- when spreading messages about processes and events taking place in the world;
- it finds its expression in the awakening in people, the general public, the masses of the desire to actively participate in the changes taking place in the country.

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